

Therapeutic Efficacy of Chloroquine plus Primaquine in the Treatment of Uncomplicated Plasmodium Vivax Malaria in Shecha Health Center

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MRLRR | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13255748>

ABSTRACT

Background: Declining efficacy of chloroquine against Plasmodium vivax malaria has been documented in Ethiopia. Thus, there is a need to assess the efficacy of combination schizontocidal and gametocidal anti-malarials such as chloroquine plus primaquine in Plasmodium vivax malaria-infected patients. The aim of this study was to assess therapeutic efficacy of chloroquine plus primaquine in the treatment of uncomplicated Plasmodium vivax in Shecha Health Center, South Ethiopia.

Methods: This is a single-arm therapeutic efficacy study in Shecha Health Center, South Ethiopia, involved 88 Plasmodium vivax participants. They were monitored for 42 days and treated with chloroquine and primaquine. World Health Organization standard data collection tool was used to collect laboratory parameters and clinical data. Data analysis included Kaplan-Meier survival analysis and Statistical Package for Social Sciences version-26 software. A P-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: The study involved 88 participants, with 98.8% completing their 42-day follow-up period. The drug had a cure rate of 96.7% before PCR and 100% after PCR, with a parasitemia-free rate of 93.2%.

Conclusions: Chloroquine plus primaquine remains effective in treating uncomplicated Plasmodium Vivax malaria, resulting in rapid clearance, fever reduction, hemoglobin improvement, and clinical resolution.

Key words: Chloroquine, Efficacy, Plasmodium vivax, Primaquine

Citation: Dinka Dugassa, Bockretsion Gidey, Busha Gamachu. Therapeutic Efficacy of Chloroquine plus Primaquine in the Treatment of Uncomplicated Plasmodium Vivax Malaria in Shecha Health Center. The 2nd Annual MRL Research Conference, Zenodo; August 15, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13255748>

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